

Modeling for size of damage-causing generation of rice leaffolder (LF)

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Second-generation LF *Cnaphalocrocis medinalis* Guenée (Jun-10 Jul) is the most damaging in Jiangxi Province, Yangtze River region. To predict the size of this generation, we used error analysis (or key factor analysis) to select in sequence environmental factors. The selection criterion is a correlation coefficient larger than 0.53. The model's multiple regression formula is:

$$\log N_2 = -6.6025 + 0.7387 \log N_1 - 7.1912 \log T_4 + 17.3500 \log S_5 - 2.0791$$

$$\log W_8 + 1.0313 \log M_4 + 0.9988 \log T_5 - 0.7634 \log P_{12} - 0.2267 \log R_5.$$

N_2 is emergence size of second generation, N_1 is emergence size of first generation, T_4 is average air temperature in Apr, S_5 is sea temperature in No. 25 region of Northwest Pacific in May, W_8 is back spot site of subtropical air pressure in late Aug, M_4 is terrestrial magnetism index in Apr, T_5 is minimum temperature in May, P_{12} is water vapor pressure in late Dec, and R_5 is total monthly rainfall in May. Correlation coefficient of the formula is 0.9885, $F = 9.19$, $df = 7.7$, $P < 0.001$.

The figure shows the emergence size in 1965-79 and predicted size of second-generation LF. $\mathcal{J}$

Emergence size and predicted size of second-generation LF at Jian prefecture, Jiangxi Province, China, 1965-79.

Brain cells and chromosomes of the brown planthopper *Nilaparvata lugens* (Stål)

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Standard air-drying techniques with lacto-aceto-orcein staining were used to observe the mitotic brain cells and chromosomes of fourth-instar *N. lugens* nymphs (Fig. 1). From 100 individuals, the mean number of cells undergoing mitosis was 487; the mean number of nondividing cells was 247, for a 67% mitotic index.

Premetaphase chromosome counts established the normal diploid complement at $2n = 30$. The karyotype included 28 autosomes and an XX (female) or XY (male) sex chromosome system. The sex chromosomes were heterochromatic and maximally contracted. The XX or XY tandem consisted of chromosomes which were smaller than or equal to some autosomes. The X and the Y chromosomes usually had different shapes; the X-chromosome was always bigger than the Y-chromosome.

Early metakinetic chromosomes (Fig. 1b, c, e, f, g, and i) were short and

1. Brain cells and chromosomes of *N. lugens* biotype 1. IRR, 1986. Magnification 1000X (oil immersion).

rod-shaped; each chromosome had two chromatids. The sister chromatids comprising the chromosomes were barely observable because of the lack of a distinct centromere. They appeared to have diffuse or scattered spindle attachments, implying that *N. lugens* chromosomes are holokinetic. At metaphase, the chromosomes occupied the spindle body with the chromosomal long axis at right angles to the polar axis.

Total chromatin was 11.90μ in female and 5.74μ in male *N. lugens*. Females possessed longer chromosomes (Fig. 1c) than males (Fig. 1b and e). However, the reverse was the case in relative mean lengths.

In karyotype analysis of

2. Relative mean lengths of premetaphase brain chromosomes of male (A) and female (B) *N. lugens* biotype 1. IRR, 1986. Magnification 1000X (oil immersion).